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**Perceived Outcomes on the Management Sustainability of Western
Philippines University External Campuses**

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ABSTRACT

The Western Philippines University is serving primarily the province of Palawan. The main Campus is located in San Juan, Aborlan, Palawan and another major campus is located at Puerto Princesa City. Different campuses and training centers are established in the strategic places in the province operating in partnership with the Local Government Units (LGUs). Findings of the study would serve as basis of Western Philippines University External Campuses administration to further enhance and develop shared governance; governance structure and external influences. This research study aimed to determine the perceived outcomes on the management sustainability of Western Philippines University-External Campuses". Specifically, it analyzed the significant relationship between the management competence of the campus administrators and the perceived outcomes on the management sustainability of External Campuses as to instruction, research and extension services. This study was conducted at the Western Philippines University External Campuses namely: Quezon Campus, Busuanga Campus, El Nido Campus, Culion Campus, Canique Extension School and Rio Tuba Extension School. This study used the descriptive-correlational research method. Descriptive method was employed to describe the management capability of the administrators according to management competence and the perceived outcomes of management which was the sustainability of the WPU-External Campuses in terms of instruction, research and extension.

INTRODUCTION

Background

The Western Philippines University is serving primarily the province of Palawan. The main Campus is located in San Juan, Aborlan, Palawan and another major campus is located at Puerto Princesa City. Different campuses and training centers are established in the strategic places in the province operating in partnership with the Local Government Units (LGUs). Findings of the study would serve as basis of Western Philippines University

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External Campuses administration to further enhance and develop shared governance; governance structure and external influences.

Objectives

This research study aimed to determine the perceived outcomes on the management sustainability of Western Philippines University-External Campuses". Specifically, it analysed the significant relationship between the management competence of the campus administrators and the perceived outcomes on the management sustainability of External Campuses as to instruction, research and extension services.

Methodology

This study was conducted at the Western Philippines University External Campuses namely: Quezon Campus, Busuanga Campus, El Nido Campus, Culion Campus, Canique Extension School and Rio Tuba Extension School. This study used the descriptive-correlational research method. Descriptive method was employed to describe the management capability of the administrators according to management competence and the perceived outcomes of management which was the sustainability of the WPU-External Campuses in terms of instruction, research and extension. On the other hand, correlational research was utilized to assess the relationship between management of Western Philippines University External Campuses and the sustainability of External Campuses.

Results and Key Findings

Perceived Outcomes of Management as to the Sustainability of WPU External Campuses

Tables 1a-1d present the outcomes of management as to the sustainability of the Western Philippines University External Campuses in terms of instruction, research, and extension whether they are "*Highly Sustainable*" (4.50-5.00); "*Sustainable*" (3.50-4.49); "*Moderately Sustainable*" (2.50-3.49); "*Barely Sustainable*" (1.50-2.49) and "*Not Sustainable*" (1.00-1.49).

In Terms of Instruction

Table a presents the outcomes of management as to the sustainability of the External Campuses in terms of instruction as perceived by the respondents.

With a mean rating of 3.49, the five groups of respondents described the outcome of management of WPU External Campuses in terms of instruction as *moderately sustainable*.

Accordingly, respondents assessed the following aspects as *sustainable*: the LGU provides financial support and subsidies of the faculty salaries (3.91); the programs aim to achieve with its teaching, research and service to society (3.64); linkages with different agencies that provide employment to the graduates (3.64); opportunity is available at all times for WPU External Campuses graduates (3.59); teaching and learning constantly address critical national human resources requirements (3.58); LGU and business establishments preferred to hire graduates from External Campuses (3.55); the LGU provides support to the instructional capability of the faculty of the External Campuses (3.54); the External Campuses provide graduates with broad skills in teaching career (3.53); government offices preferred to accept graduates from External Campuses (3.52); and graduates from WPU External Campuses can acquire work/job in a short period of time (3.50). On the other hand, they assessed the following aspects as *moderately sustainable*: the External Campus deploys learning opportunities appropriate to the learning outcomes (3.48); the External

Campuses has approved and widely disseminated teaching and learning policy (3.48); the findings from monitoring and evaluation, and benchmarking practices are used to continuously improve learning facilitation activities (3.47); the External Campus has sufficient, qualified and experienced faculty/instructor (3.46); the graduates are competitive (3.45); the External Campuses sharpen the analytical skills of the graduates (3.43); graduates acquired knowledge and skills applicable to a career (3.42); the graduates are ready to take the challenge of the latest trend in education (3.37); there are mechanisms in place for monitoring and evaluation of the learning facilitation activities with reference to international best practices (3.35); and qualifications, scholarly work and continuing professional development are met (2.86).

The results reveal that parents and SSC officers, described the instructional outcomes of External Campuses as *sustainable*, with ratings of 3.60 and 3.50 respectively, implying that they are optimistic about the sustainability of External Campuses as far as instruction is concerned. While the faculty and staff the Barangay/LGU officials and campus administrators rated this aspect as *moderately sustainable* with ratings of 3.47; 3.46; and 3.42, respectively.

The over-all passing percentage in the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) in Quezon Campus ranges from as high as 100% in 2008 to as low as 33.33% in 2013 for Bachelor in Elementary Education and from 40% in 2007 to 100% in 2012 for Bachelor in Elementary Education, revealed that the quality of instruction in the External Campuses is highly competitive.

Findings imply that the operation of the External Campuses in terms of instruction is *sustainable*. Such finding was attributed to the support provided by the university in terms of planning, policy, transparency, communication, close monitoring and supervision and other support needed for the operation of the campuses. The hard working and dedicated personnel also contributed to the sustainability of the campus as well as the continued financial support amounted to Php5,630,000.00 annually provided by the Barangay/Local Government Unit Officials for the salary of the faculty and staff and other operational expenses.

The External Campuses have 11 regular faculties, 47 contract of service and part timers. Majority of the faculty (58.62. %) are bachelor's degree holder, 13.79 percent finished their master's degree, 15.52% with masters' degree units, 6.9% with PhD units and 5.17% are holding a diploma certificate serving as their work force. There are 15 faculties who have attended 7 different trainings (WPU-External Campuses Annual Report, 2014).

However, there is a need for further improvement as far as instruction is concerned more particularly on the faculty profile. Hence, the continuing development programs for the faculty and more trainings in line with their specialization have been provided by the management to enhance their capabilities.

The External Campuses have a total student population of 1,125 during the First Semester of School Year 2015-2016 and produced 1,370 graduates for 22 years of their existence. A memorandum of agreement was signed between the university and the hotel and resort owners in Coron and Busuanga, Palawan for the On the Job Training of Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management students.

This implies that WPU External Campuses have strong linkages with different agencies that provide employment to the graduates. It further implies that opportunity is available at all times for WPU External Campuses graduates. Furthermore, the SSC officers and the students are optimistic that after finishing the course at External Campuses, they are equipped with the skills and knowledge that will allow them to acquire employment. Thus, administrators should prepare students not only during enrolment but also for employment and should strengthen the campus placement office.

Such findings are aligned to the five-year (2011-2016) strategic plan of CHED that in order to produce highly competent and competitive graduates, HEIs are encouraged to offer programs that are in demand and responsive to the needs of the industry, both domestic and international.

World Bank (2015) mentioned that human capital development requires that every citizen is given equitable opportunity to learn, to be educated and provided with the appropriate competencies needed for wage or self-employment and become productive citizens of the country. They also insisted that graduates must not only be well-trained, entrepreneurial and confident, but also ready to contribute to the economy and serve society. Further, they added that educated individuals are more employable, able to earn higher wages, cope better with economics shocks, and raise healthier children.

Table 1a. Outcomes of management as to the sustainability of the External Campuses in terms of instruction as perceived by the respondents.

Aspect	Administrator f(n=6)		Faculty/ Staff f(n=65)		Bgy./LGU Officials f(n=87)		SSC Officers f(n=107)		Parents f(n=107)		Total f(n=372)	
	MR	DR	MR	DR	MR	DR	MR	DR	MR	DR	MR	DR
	The External Campus has sufficient, qualified and experienced faculty/instructor.	3.50	S	3.43	MS	3.44	MS	3.48	MS	3.43	MS	3.46
The External Campus has approved and widely disseminated teaching and learning policy.	3.50	S	3.52	S	3.49	MS	3.45	MS	3.41	MS	3.48	MS
The External Campus deploys learning opportunities appropriate to the learning outcomes.	3.50	S	3.54	S	3.43	MS	3.48	MS	3.45	MS	3.48	MS
Teaching and learning constantly address critical national human resources requirements.	3.67	S	3.65	S	3.44	MS	3.49	MS	3.67	S	3.58	S
Qualifications, scholarly work and continuing professional development are met.	2.83	MS	2.98	MS	2.71	MS	2.97	MS	2.79	MS	2.86	MS
There are mechanisms in place for monitoring and evaluation of the learning facilitation activities with reference to international best practices.	3.33	MS	3.37	MS	3.33	MS	3.45	MS	3.25	MS	3.35	MS
The findings from monitoring and evaluation, and benchmarking practices are used to continuously improve learning facilitation activities.	3.50	S	3.65	S	3.28	MS	3.47	MS	3.45	MS	3.47	MS

Table 1a. (continued) . . .

Aspect	Administra tor		Faculty/ Staff		Bgy./LGU Officials		SSC Officers		Parents		Total	
	f(n=6)		f(n=65)		f(n=87)		f(n=107)		f(n=107)		f(n=372)	
	MR	DR	MR	DR	MR	DR	MR	DR	MR	DR	MR	DR
The LGU provides support to the instructional capability of the faculty of the External Campuses.	3.50	S	3.55	S	3.59	S	3.38	MS	3.66	S	3.54	S
The LGU provides financial support and subsidies of the faculty salaries.	3.50	S	3.66	S	4.60	S	3.80	S	3.97	S	3.91	S
The programs aim to achieve with its teaching, research and service to society.	3.67	S	3.69	S	3.55	S	3.60	S	3.71	S	3.64	S
The graduates are ready to take the challenge of the latest trend in education.	3.17	MS	3.29	MS	3.31	MS	3.54	S	3.54	S	3.37	MS
Graduates acquired knowledge and skills applicable to a career.	3.33	MS	3.22	MS	3.47	MS	3.55	S	3.55	S	3.42	MS
The graduates are competitive.	3.33	MS	3.43	MS	3.33	MS	3.59	S	3.55	S	3.45	MS
The External Campus provides graduates with broad skills in teaching career.	3.33	MS	3.42	MS	3.46	MS	3.63	S	3.80	S	3.53	S
The External Campus sharpens the analytical skills of the graduates.	3.33	MS	3.40	MS	3.30	MS	3.43	MS	3.70	S	3.43	MS
Government offices preferred to accept graduates from External Campuses.	3.33	MS	3.46	MS	3.53	S	3.48	MS	3.80	S	3.52	S
LGU and business establishment preferred to hire graduates from External Campuses.	3.33	MS	3.43	MS	3.56	S	3.60	S	3.81	S	3.55	S
Graduates from WPU External Campuses can acquired work/job in a short period of time.	3.33	MS	3.42	MS	3.40	MS	3.53	S	3.80	S	3.50	S

Table 1a. (continued) ...

Aspect	Administrator		Faculty/Staff		Bgy./LGU Officials		SSC Officers		Parents		Total	
	f(n=6)		f(n=65)		f(n=87)		f(n=107)		f(n=107)		f(n=372)	
	MR	DR	MR	DR	MR	DR	MR	DR	MR	DR	MR	DR
The WPU External Campuses have linkages with different agencies that provide employment of the graduates.	3.67	S	3.71	S	3.49	MS	3.53	S	3.80	S	3.64	S
Opportunity is available at all times for WPU External Campuses graduate.	3.67	S	3.54	S	3.47	MS	3.47	MS	3.81	S	3.59	S
Grand mean: 3.49	3.42	MS	3.47	MS	3.46	MS	3.50	S	3.60	S	3.49	MS

Legend:

- 4.50 – 5.00 - *Highly Sustainable*
- 3.50 – 4.49 - *Sustainable*
- 2.50 – 3.49 - *Moderately Sustainable*
- 1.50 – 2.49 - *Barely Sustainable*
- 1.00 – 1.49 - *Not Sustainable*

In Terms of Research

Table 1b shows the outcomes of management as to the sustainability of the External Campuses in terms of research as perceived by the respondents. It reveals that respondents assessed the sustainability of the External Campuses in terms of research as *moderately sustainable* (2.84).

However, in the statement that the research activities of the External Campuses reflect the mission and goals of the institution the respondents assessed as sustainable (3.61). On the other hand, the respondents gave a *moderately sustainable* rating on the following aspects: the External Campuses provide research programs concerned with the judicious utilization, protection and rehabilitation of the local natural resources and habitat (3.46); the LGU gives support to the conduct of faculty and student research (3.04); the External Campuses conduct research that responds to socio-cultural and sports activities of the community particularly (2.98); the External Campuses upgrade the capabilities of extension services personnel/faculty and staff through research trainings (2.89); the LGU and the External Campuses disseminate the results of conducted research for the improvement of services delivery (2.53); the External Campus as an institution has formulated a code of conduct and a code of ethics in research (2.50); the External Campus has formulated a policy to protect intellectual property rights (2.50). However, the respondents gave a *barely sustainable* assessment on the following: The External Campuses have an approved and widely disseminated research policy (2.46); and the External Campus as an institution has a Research Ethics Committee (2.46).

Results show that the Barangay/Local Government Unit officials gave a rating (2.90) described as *moderately sustainable* in terms of research, followed by faculty and staff

(2.87), campus administrators (2.85), parents (2.84) and SSC officers (2.76). They all believed that the External Campuses need to be sustainable in research development. Findings implied that research activities are less prioritized in the External Campuses. However, as a requirement, the students taking up a BS degree should conduct their research to finish their chosen courses. Thus, the External Campuses students have already conducted a total of 472 researches, while the faculty had presented only seven researches in the national research forum. The External Campuses faculty should therefore conduct more researches for the development of the school and the community. As pointed out by the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (2009), that as society becomes increasingly knowledge-based, the greater the role of higher learning and research in enhancing the cultural, social, economic and environmental aspects of sustainable development of individuals, communities and nations.

Table 1b. Outcomes of management as to the sustainability of the External Campuses in terms of research as perceived by the respondents.

Aspect	Administrator		Faculty/Staff		Bgy./LGU Officials		SSC Officers		Parents		Total	
	f(n=6)		f(n=65)		f(n=87)		f(n=107)		f(n=107)		f(n=372)	
	MR	DR	MR	DR	MR	DR	MR	DR	MR	DR	MR	DR
The External Campus has an approved and widely disseminated research policy.	2.50	MS	2.46	BS	2.45	BS	2.41	BS	2.49	BS	2.46	BS
The External Campus has formulated a policy to protect intellectual property rights.	2.50	MS	2.51	MS	2.48	BS	2.49	BS	2.50	MS	2.50	MS
The External Campus as an institution has formulated a code of conduct and a code of ethics in research.	2.50	MS	2.51	MS	2.47	BS	2.40	BS	2.64	MS	2.50	MS
The External Campus as an institution has Research Ethics Committee.	2.50	MS	2.51	MS	2.47	BS	2.39	BS	2.41	BS	2.46	BS
The research activities reflect the mission and goals of the institutions.	3.67	S	3.65	S	3.57	S	3.62	S	3.56	S	3.61	S
The LGU gives support to the conduct of faculty and student research.	2.67	MS	2.78	MS	3.80	S	2.96	MS	2.97	MS	3.04	MS
The External Campuses conduct research that responds to socio-cultural and sports activities of the community.	3.00	MS	3.02	MS	2.98	MS	2.93	MS	2.99	MS	2.98	MS

Table 1b. (continued) ...

Aspect	Administrator		Faculty/Staff		Bgy./LGU Officials		SSC Officers		Parents		Total	
	f(n=6)		f(n=65)		f(n=87)		f(n=107)		f(n=107)		f(n=372)	
	MR	DR	MR	DR	MR	DR	MR	DR	MR	DR	MR	DR
The External Campuses disseminate the results of conducted research for the improvement of services delivery.	2.67	MS	2.85	MS	2.34	BS	2.29	BS	2.51	MS	2.53	MS
The External Campuses provide research programs concerned with the judicious utilization, protection and rehabilitation of the local natural resources and habitat.	3.67	S	3.65	S	3.36	MS	3.30	MS	3.35	MS	3.46	MS
The LGU and the External Campuses upgrade capabilities of extension services personnel/faculty and staff through research trainings.	2.83	MS	2.82	MS	3.02	MS	2.79	MS	2.99	MS	2.89	MS
Grand Mean: 2.84	2.85	MS	2.87	MS	2.90	MS	2.76	MS	2.84	MS	2.84	MS

Legend:

- 4.50 – 5.00 - *Highly Sustainable*
- 3.50 – 4.49 - *Sustainable*
- 2.50 – 3.49 - *Moderately Sustainable*
- 1.50 – 2.49 - *Barely Sustainable*
- 1.00 – 1.49 - *Not Sustainable*

In Terms of Extension

Table 1c shows the outcomes of management as to the sustainability of the External Campuses in terms of extension as perceived by the respondents.

It is reflected in the table that the External Campuses are *sustainable* (3.74) in terms of extension. They are *highly sustainable* (4.75) with their strong partnership and collaborative effort for community development.

Accordingly, respondents assessed the following aspects as *sustainable*: the External Campuses have partnership program with local government units (LGUs) and other institutions aimed at supporting countryside development by mobilizing local personnel/faculty and available resources of the University (4.07); the LGU supports the External Campuses in the conduct of relevant extension activities in the locality (3.98); the community/locale people are supportive to the extension activities of the External Campuses (3.89); the External Campuses have training activities extended by a department or college to clients, LGUs, and community beneficiaries and their target groups (3.86); the LGU gives financial support to the extension activities (3.85). On the other hand, the respondents described the following aspects as *moderately sustainable*: the External Campuses have program that focuses on the transfer of skills, knowledge, expertise and know-how (3.46); provide different technological and vocational expertise of the University accessible and useful to the community and business through deployment of technical experts from the university (3.45); have an approved and widely disseminated community engagement policy (3.07) and have clear guidelines for consultancy and community engagement (3.04). The Barangay/Local

Government Unit officials gave the highest assessment (3.92); followed by the parents (3.86); SSC officers (3.73); administrators (3.65); and the faculty and staff (3.54). Result implies that External Campuses have strong partnership and collaborative effort with the local government for community development and have a program focused on the transfer of skills, knowledge, expertise and know-how. In 2014, the External Campuses conducted four (4) trainings to 399 individuals. A community was adopted which is considered as a community outreach and part of extension activities of the faculty and students in Sitio Ladayon, Barangay Sowangan, Quezon, Palawan. However, a survey on needs assessment must be instituted to gather the necessary information and be properly validated with the community before the implementation of any extension activities. This finding conforms to the study of Nostratis (2011) mentioning that the Western Philippines University has implemented collaborative research and extension projects. Hence, the External Campuses of the Western Philippines University should practice and conduct extension activities as one of the tri-fold functions of the university. Ngok Thach (2008) asserted that through the community extension program, the entire academic community is not only provided with opportunities to be aware of, and understand the needs and problems that are prevalent on both local and national levels but also opportunities to involve itself in activities designed to develop the community and the less privileged. He clarifies further that to make the community extension program of the school a successful endeavor, the program must cascade from the mission and vision of the school. This means that the instruction and research agenda of the school should result towards the realization of the objectives of the extension office or council. Neda *et al.* (2009) mentioned that working with other agencies, organization and groups is a part of the extension philosophy as it brings people together and link various resources. In other words, extension work is made possible by the expertise and knowledge of the academic discipline of the staff members who are providing such service and is rooted in rigorous academic work of the staff members concerned.

Table 1c. Outcomes of management as to the sustainability of the External Campuses in terms of extension as perceived by the respondents.

Aspect	Administrator		Faculty/Staff		Bgy./LGU Officials		SSC Officers		Parents		Total	
	f(n=6)		f(n=65)		f(n=87)		f(n=107)		f(n=107)		f(n=372)	
	MR	DR	MR	DR	MR	DR	MR	DR	MR	DR	MR	DR
The External Campus has an approved and widely disseminated community engagement policy.	3.17	MS	3.00	MS	3.02	MS	3.14	MS	3.00	MS	3.07	MS
The External Campus has clear guidelines for consultancy and community engagement.	3.00	MS	3.09	MS	3.03	MS	3.01	MS	3.05	MS	3.04	MS
The External Campus provides different technological and vocational through the deployment of technical experts from the university.	3.33	MS	3.38	MS	3.36	MS	3.57	S	3.62	S	3.45	MS
The External Campuses have program focuses on the transfer of skills, knowledge, expertise, know-how.	3.33	MS	3.40	MS	3.39	MS	3.55	S	3.61	S	3.46	MS
The External Campus has strong partnership and collaborative effort for community development.	5.00	HS	4.69	HS	4.70	HS	4.69	HS	4.68	HS	4.75	HS
The LGU supports the External Campuses in the conduct of relevant extension activities in the locality.	3.67	S	3.66	S	4.64	HS	3.83	S	4.10	S	3.98	S

Table 1c. (continued) . . .

Aspect	Administrator		Faculty/Staff		Bgy./LGU Officials		SSC Officers		Parents		Total	
	f(n=6)		f(n=65)		f(n=87)		f(n=107)		f(n=107)		f(n=372)	
	MR	DR	MR	DR	MR	DR	MR	DR	MR	DR	MR	DR
The community/locale people are supportive to the extension activities of the External Campuses.	3.67	S	3.58	S	4.20	S	3.71	S	4.30	S	3.89	S
The LGU gives financial support to the extension activities.	3.33	MS	3.35	MS	4.51	HS	4.04	S	4.00	S	3.85	S
The External Campuses have partnership program with local government units (LGUs) and other institutions aimed at supporting countryside development by mobilizing local personnel/faculty and available resources of the University.	4.00	S	3.69	S	4.52	HS	4.04	S	4.09	S	4.07	S
The External Campuses have training activities extended by a department or college to clients, LGUs, and community beneficiaries and their target groups.	4.00	S	3.54	S	3.83	S	3.76	S	4.15	S	3.86	S
Grand Mean: 3.74	3.65	S	3.54	S	3.92	S	3.73	S	3.86	S	3.74	S

Legend:

- 4.50 – 5.00 - *Highly Sustainable*
- 3.50 – 4.49 - *Sustainable*
- 2.50 – 3.49 - *Moderately Sustainable*
- 1.50 – 2.49 - *Barely Sustainable*
- 1.00 – 1.49 - *Not Sustainable*

The summary of the outcomes of management which is the sustainability of the WPU External Campuses as perceived by the respondents is presented in Table 1d. It reveals that extension (3.74) was rated as *sustainable*, while instruction (3.49) and research (2.84) were rated as *moderately sustainable*. Generally, at 3.36 described as *moderately sustainable*, it implies that External Campuses can sustain their operation due to the strong partnership of the Western Philippines University and the stakeholders. Likewise, External Campuses provide the relevant knowledge and skills to meet labor market needs of the society. Such finding was supported by Nostratis (2011) that the Western Philippines University created an impact to the development of Palawan. She further mentioned that the university's instruction, research, extension and production activities have made a positive difference in the lives of many Palaweños. However, there is really a need to strengthen the instruction, research and extension for the sustainability of External Campuses.

According to Klein (2013), the power of collective capacity is that it enables ordinary people to accomplish extraordinary things for two reasons. One is that knowledge about effective practice becomes more widely available and accessible on a daily basis. The second reason is more powerful still that working together generates commitment.

Table 1d. Summary table on the outcomes of management of the WPU External Campuses as perceived by the respondents.

Perceived Outcomes	Mean Rating	Descriptive Rating
Instruction	3.49	Moderately Sustainable
Research	2.84	Moderately Sustainable
Extension	3.74	Sustainable
Grand Mean	3.36	Moderately Sustainable

Legend:

- 4.50 – 5.00 - *Highly Sustainable*
- 3.50 – 4.49 - *Sustainable*
- 2.50 – 3.49 - *Moderately Sustainable*
- 1.50 – 2.49 - *Barely Sustainable*
- 1.00 – 1.49 - *Not Sustainable*

Relationship between the Management Competence of the Campus Administrators and the Perceived Outcomes of Management

Table 2 presents the significant relationship between management competence of the campus administrators and the perceived outcomes of management as to the sustainability of WPU External Campuses.

It can be noted that instruction and extension are factors to the perceived outcomes of management as manifested by their P-values of 0.000 and 0.021 which are less than 0.05 level of significance.

This means that the null hypothesis that “there is no significant relationship between management competence of the campus administrators and the perceived outcomes of management as to the sustainability of WPU External Campuses” is rejected along instruction and extension.

The same null hypothesis is accepted along research as shown by its P-value of 0.356 which is greater than 0.05 level of significance. This implies that research does not determine the management competence of the campus administrators.

Result shows that the management competence of the campus administrators had significant relationship when it comes to the sustainability of the External Campuses as to instruction and extension activities. However, it has low or weak relationship as to the research activities. This implies that the management competence of the campus administrators cannot influence their faculty to do researches due to the fact that most of their faculty (81%) or 47 out of 58 are contract of service and part timers and they are receiving their salary from the Local Government Units. Moreover, their exposure to research fora is another great factor to consider. Aside from instruction, the campus administrators also play multi responsibilities such as librarian, collection officer, registrar, and other tasks which required a lot of time.

Results further implied that the ability of the campus administrators to lead with collective efforts resulted into more productive outcomes. Furthermore, the sustainability on the operation of the External Campuses depends mostly on the ability of the campus administrators on how to gain the all out support of the university top management as well as the community through the Barangay/Local Government Units.

This was supported by Bryk *et al.* (2010) mentioning that, strong ties among school personnel, parents, and community service providers, with an integrated support network for students as well as leadership focused on cultivating teachers, parents, and community members so that they became invested in sharing responsibility for the school's improvement are among the evidences of collaboration for the success of school.

Ronfeldt *et al.* (2011) found that students performed worse when teacher turnover within their grade-level team was higher. Further they insisted that keeping teacher turnover low and cultivating an atmosphere of trust are important goals because they pave the way for increased student achievement.

Louis *et al.* (2010) found that “school leaders have an impact on student achievement primarily through their influence on teachers’ motivation and working conditions.”

Table 2. Relationship between the management competence of the campus administrators and perceived outcomes of management.

Perceived Outcomes	Pearson r	P-value	Decision
Instruction	0.236**	0.000	H ₀ : reject
Research	0.048	0.356	H ₀ : accept
Extension	0.120*	0.021	H ₀ : reject

* significant at $\alpha = 0.05$

** significant at $\alpha = 0.01$

Relationship between the Decision Making Style of the Campus Administrators and the Sustainability of the External Campuses

Table 9 presents the significant relationship between decision making style of the campus administrators and the perceived outcomes of management as to the sustainability of WPU External Campuses.

Instruction and extension are factors to the perceived outcomes of management as manifested by their P-values of 0.000 and 0.021 which are less than 0.05 level of significance.

This means that the null hypothesis that “there is no significant relationship between decision making style of the campus administrators and the perceived outcomes of management as to the sustainability of WPU External Campuses” is rejected along instruction and extension.

The same null hypothesis is accepted along research as shown by its P-value of 0.356 which is greater than 0.05 level of significance. This shows that research does not influence the decision-making style of the campus administrators.

Result shows that the decision making style of the campus administrators has a significant relationship when it comes to the sustainability of the External Campuses as to instruction and extension activities. However, it has low or weak relationship to the research activities. Result implies that the decision making style of the campus administrators cannot influence their faculty to do researches particularly to those contract of service and part timers. Another reality is that faculty particularly those contract of service are handling 28-32 contact hours of teaching, their exposure to research fora also of great factors to be considered.

Results further implied that the decision making style of the campus administrators has a great contribution to sustain the operation of the External Campuses.

Table 3. Relationship between the decision making style of the campus administrators and the sustainability of the External Campuses.

Perceived Outcomes	Pearson r	P-value	Decision
Instruction	0.340**	0.000	H ₀ : reject
Research	0.034	0.356	H ₀ : accept
Extension	0.186**	0.021	H ₀ : reject

* significant at $\alpha = 0.05$

** significant at $\alpha = 0.01$

Summary

This study aimed to determine the management of WPU External Campuses as perceived by the respondents. Specifically, it assessed the management of WPU External Campuses, management capability of the campus administrators, the perceived outcomes of management as to the sustainability of WPU External Campuses. Further, it analyzed the significant relationship between management of WPU External Campuses and management competence of the campus administrators, between the perceived outcomes of management, the sustainability of the External Campuses.

This study was conducted to six administrators, 65 faculty and staff, 107 SSC officers, 107 parents and 87 Barangay/Local Government Unit officials from Western Philippines University External Campuses namely: Quezon Campus, Busuanga Campus, El Nido Campus, Culion Campus, Canique Extension School and Rio Tuba Extension School.

The parallel researcher-made survey questionnaires were used. The data were analysed through the use of descriptive statistics. Further, the respondents assessed the sustainability of the External Campuses in terms of extension as *sustainable* (3.74), while instruction (3.49), and research (2.84) as *moderately sustainable*.

Conclusions

Based on the significant findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Campus Administrators affect the management and the sustainability of the External Campuses.
2. The Barangay/Local Government officials, faculty, parents and students strongly believe as to the capability of the Campus Administrators in the aspects of management, management competence and its outcomes.

Recommendations

After a thorough examination of the findings and conclusions of the study, the researcher recommended the following:

For the WPU Administration

1. Continuously support the WPU External Campuses towards their improvement, development and sustainability.
2. Establish strong linkages to different GOs' and NGOs' and to the LGU for the management and governance of the External Campuses.

For the Campus Administrator

1. Develop and lead a successful governance, management and its outcomes for the educational improvement partnership among school, teachers and stakeholders.
2. Work hand in hand with the WPU administration and stakeholders to attain the school development.
3. Maintain a collaborative effort with faculty/staff and provide opportunities for shared leadership to support the shared common vision of the university.
4. Develop stronger relationship and camaraderie with the LGU's, NGO's GO's teachers and stakeholders.
5. Continuously provide close supervision and instructional guidance to your teachers.
6. Provide continuous communication and facilitation on the needs of the school.
7. Support research and extension activities of faculty.
8. Prepare and implement research and training programs for faculty with budgetary requirements.
9. Provide programs for the development of the school, the community and the graduates.
10. Establish close relationship and camaraderie with your colleagues and stakeholders.

For the Faculty

1. Cooperate with your respective Campus Administrators in the management of the school.
2. Establish close relationship and camaraderie with the administrators and stakeholders.
3. Conduct faculty research for the improvement and development of the school, support the extension activities and development of the community.

For Future Research/Researcher

1. Similar research study be conducted in the other External Campuses of other colleges and universities in the country.

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